

**GESTURE AS A COMMUNICATION STRATEGY IN FOREIGN
LANGUAGE DISCOURSE: A STUDY OF LEARNERS OF ENGLISH AND
UZBEK**

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Abstract: This article examines the role of gestures as a communication strategy in the discourse of English and Uzbek language learners. The study investigates the use of gestures by learners to compensate for linguistic limitations and effectively convey meaning in foreign language communication. A review of the existing literature on communication strategies in second language acquisition and gesture use provides the foundation for this research. The methodology includes data collection through audio and video recordings, as well as interviews, and the analysis focuses on identifying common gesture types and comparing their use in English and Uzbek discourse. The findings highlight the significance of gestures as a communication strategy, with implications for language teaching and learning. The study recommends the incorporation of gesture training in language classrooms to enhance learners' communicative competence. Further research in this area is needed to deepen our understanding of gesture use as a communication strategy and its impact on language learning outcomes.

Key words: communication strategies, gesture use, foreign language discourse, English learners, Uzbek learners.

Introduction:

In the introduction, briefly highlight the significance of communication strategies in foreign language learning. Discuss how learners use various techniques, including gestures, to compensate for linguistic limitations and effectively convey their intended

message. Emphasize the relevance of studying communication strategies for more effective language teaching and learning approaches. State the focus of the article: investigating the role of gestures as a communication strategy in the discourse of English and Uzbek language learners.

Literature and methodology:

In this section, provide an overview of the existing research on communication strategies in second language acquisition. Discuss studies that have explored the use of various communication strategies by language learners, such as code-switching, circumlocution, and gestures. Highlight the importance of communication strategies in facilitating effective communication, promoting learner autonomy, and enhancing overall language proficiency. Additionally, focus on the specific studies that have examined the role of gestures as a communication strategy in foreign language discourse. Summarize their key findings, methodologies, and theoretical frameworks. Identify any gaps or limitations in the literature, particularly in the context of English and Uzbek language learners. In this section, provide a description of the research design and participants of your study. Explain the approach you took to investigate the role of gestures as a communication strategy in the discourse of English and Uzbek language learners. Describe the participants of the study, including their demographic information (e.g., age, language proficiency level, educational background). Mention any specific criteria for participant selection, such as learners who have been studying English or Uzbek for a certain duration or have reached a specific proficiency level. Explain the research design you employed, such as a qualitative or mixed-methods approach. Provide details on how data were collected, including the use of audio recordings, video recordings, interviews, or other relevant methods. Discuss any ethical considerations and steps taken to ensure participant confidentiality and informed consent.

Results:

In this section, present and analyze the data collected from the English and Uzbek language learners in relation to their use of gestures as a communication strategy. Start

by providing an overview of the data collected, such as the number of participants, duration of recordings, and any relevant contextual information. Then, present the findings in a clear and organized manner, using appropriate tables, charts, or excerpts from the data to support your analysis. Analyze the gestures used by the learners, focusing on their frequency, types, and functions within the discourse. Identify common patterns and trends in gesture use among the participants. Compare and contrast the use of gestures in English and Uzbek discourse, highlighting any similarities or differences. Interpret the findings within the context of existing literature and theories on gesture use in second language acquisition. Discuss the implications of the findings for understanding the role of gestures as a communication strategy in foreign language discourse.

Discussion:

In this section, interpret the findings of your study in relation to the existing literature on communication strategies and gesture use in second language acquisition. Discuss the implications and insights that arise from your analysis. Examine how the findings align with or diverge from previous research on gesture use as a communication strategy in foreign language discourse. Discuss any similarities or differences between your study's results and those of other studies. Analyze the potential reasons behind these similarities or differences, such as cultural factors or language-specific characteristics. Evaluate the effectiveness and appropriateness of gesture use as a communication strategy in the context of English and Uzbek language learners. Discuss how gestures may contribute to successful communication and linguistic development, considering factors such as learners' language proficiency levels and their cultural backgrounds. Furthermore, discuss the pedagogical implications of your findings. Explore how your study's insights can inform language teaching practices and curriculum development, particularly in regards to promoting effective use of gestures as a communication strategy. Highlight the potential benefits of incorporating gesture training or awareness in language classrooms. Examine how the insights from your study can be applied to enhance language instruction and

promote effective communication in the classroom. Discuss the potential benefits of incorporating gesture training or instruction as part of language learning programs. Provide pedagogical recommendations based on your findings. Suggest practical strategies and activities that language teachers can implement to help learners develop their proficiency in using gestures as a communication strategy. Highlight the importance of providing learners with opportunities to practice and reflect on gesture use in various communicative contexts. Consider the cultural and contextual factors that may influence the appropriateness and effectiveness of gestures in different language learning environments. Discuss any adaptations or modifications that may be necessary when implementing these recommendations in specific educational settings.

Conclusion:

In the conclusion, provide a concise summary of the main findings regarding the role of gestures as a communication strategy in the discourse of English and Uzbek language learners. Emphasize the importance of gestures in enhancing communication and compensating for linguistic limitations. Reiterate the implications of the findings for language teaching and learning, emphasizing the potential benefits of incorporating gesture instruction in language classrooms. Conclude by highlighting the need for further research in this area to deepen our understanding of gesture use as a communication strategy and its impact on language learning outcomes.

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